

THE EFFECT OF PROLONGED HEAT TREATMENTS ON THE MICROSTRUCTURAL EVOLUTION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF Ti/Ni MULTI-LAYERED COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY ACCUMULATIVE ROLL BONDING (ARB)

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ABSTRACT

A study was performed to determine the influence of microstructural evolution at interfaces on the subsequent uniaxial tensile properties of Ti/Ni multilayered composites fabricated by accumulative roll bonding (ARB) and subsequent annealing. The microstructure and chemical composition of the interfaces were examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The fracture feature of the tensile samples was studied by scanning electron microscope (SEM). At longer annealing time, the diffusion regions between Ti and Ni elements from a single side changed to two sides and became thicker. The tensile strength of the annealed composites decreased initially, and then was slightly increased after 60h. The elongation increased significantly relative to the original rolled samples. Fractography revealed brittle fracture areas produced in the Ti/Ni interfaces. Ductile fracture via nucleation growth and the coalescence of micro-dimples in the Ti layer at room temperature were also observed. The failure mode in the annealed Ti/Ni composites was a typical ductile mixed brittle fracture.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metallic multi-layered composites have attracted attention due to their high strength, excellent resistant corrosion, and good physical properties [1]. Currently, laminar composites are manufactured by explosive welding [2], roll bonding [3], diffusion bonding [4], extrusion [5], and magnetic sputtering [6], but most of these processes are complex and require expensive tools which have limited more extensive application of these technologies. Accumulative roll bonding (ARB) is a severe plastic deformation (SPD) method, and offers several advantages compared with the above methods, such as low equipment requirements and high productivity. This method can be used to produce multi-layered composites that are ultra-fine grained (UFG) or nanostructured. Thus, ARB is currently one of the most widely used methods for the production of laminar composites. The ARB technique has been successfully applied for the fabrication of various metallic multi-layered composites of bi-metal systems, including Al/steel [7], Al/Mg [8,9], Al/Cu [10], Al/Ni [11-13], Al/Ti [14], Cu/Ti [15], Cu/Zn [16], Cu/Ni [17], and others.

Many properties of Ti/Ni multilayered composites have been investigated, such as the effect of heat treatment on the microstructure and the chemical composition of composite materials prepared by different manufacturing technologies, such as explosive joining [18], ion implantation [19], and diffusion bonding [20]. Other scholars have studied the mechanical properties of layered composites. For instance, Ghazal Tadayyon [21] investigated the effect of annealing on mechanical properties and the microstructural evolution of Ti-rich NiTi shape memory alloy. The results showed that annealing above the recrystallization temperature (600°C) significantly modulated the mechanical behavior of the alloy. These studies about the Ti/Ni multi-layered composite materials have focused on one or more aspects of microstructure, chemical composition, and mechanical properties. However, using ARB technique to fabricate Ti/Ni laminated composites is a relatively new issue. Our group has found that Ti/Ni multi-layered composites produced by ARB exhibit fine crystal structure and high tensile strength [1,22]. However, the effect of annealing on the interface microstructures and mechanical properties of ARBed Ti/Ni multilayered composites have not been examined, especially the influence of interfacial microstructure evolution on mechanical properties after annealing.

The main objective of the present work was to investigate the influence of interface microstructure evolution on the mechanical properties of Ti/Ni multi-layered composites produced by accumulative roll bonding (ARB) and annealing by means of SEM equipped with EDS. The diffusion phenomenon of the Ti/Ni bonding interface was observed. Tensile testing was performed on the Ti/Ni laminated composites to determine the basic mechanical properties of the composite and preliminarily explore the fracture mechanism of the composite. Based on the tensile performance of the multilayer composites, the microstructural effects on the mechanical properties of the composites were analyzed.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

We used Ti/Ni multi-layered composites at the total thickness of 0.2mm fabricated by six passes of accumulative roll bonding (ARB) and subsequent rolling to reduce the thickness of the composites from 1.05mm to 0.2mm. The multi-layered composites were formed by isothermal annealing in a muffle furnace at 300°C for 1h, 5h, 10h, or 60h. After annealing, the laminates were air-cooled to room temperature (RT). Subsequent annealing of the samples at 300°C enabled enhanced interaction and induced generation of thin diffusion layers (include intermetallic compound layers) between the Ti and Ni interfaces.

The interfacial microstructure and chemical composition of Ti/Ni composites were characterized by using a JSM-6460F scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Semi-quantitative EDS analysis was performed to estimate the composition of different diffusion phases at the Ti/Ni interface.

The mechanical properties of the laminates prepared with different annealing times were subjected to uniaxial tensile tests conducted at room temperature on an INSTRON 8801 machine operating at a constant speed of 0.1mm/min. Finally, the rupture morphologies and mechanisms of the tensile test-

fractured foils were studied by SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

The interfacial microstructure of Ti/Ni multi-layered composites rolled and annealed at 300°C for different times are shown in Figure 1. For annealed composites (Fig. 1a-d), some local diffusion protuberances first appeared in the Ni layer, suggesting atomic diffusion occurs in a certain order rather than the entire interface at the same time. This is because during rolling deformation, dislocation tangles cause regions of concentrated stress in the Ti/Ni interfaces with high potential energy to promote diffusion during the annealing process. Furthermore, from the perspective of thermodynamics conditions, the activation energy for the migration of the grain boundary and atomic motion is provided by thermal energy at 300°C. The number of diffusion atoms in the bonding interface exceeds the saturation of the Ti-Ni solid solution. Once the thermal activation is significant, the supersaturated solid solutions will transform into the intermetallic compounds [23].

The effect of annealing time on the microstructure was compared in Figure 1. With prolonging annealing time, the number of diffusion regions in the Ti/Ni bonding interfaces increased gradually and the interfacial diffusion islets of the Ti and Ni elements became longer and thicker, so the diffusion volume in the interfaces increased. With increasing annealing time, the atoms will have more stored thermal energy and can more easily reach the activation energy required for thermal motion. With more atoms thermal motion on the interface, there will be more diffusion. With increased annealing time, a new diffusion layer will be created in the original diffusion layer interface and the thickness of diffusion regions gradually increase due to the perpendicular growth of intermetallic phases along the interface. Previously, Coffey [24] obtained a similar result in the fabrication of the Al-rich phase in Al/metal multilayer material during the annealing process.

An element line scan of Ti and Ni elements was conducted using EDS to determine elemental distribution across the bonding interface after annealing. Fig. 2a shows the EDS line analysis across the interface of Ti/Ni composite annealed at 300°C for 1h. The concentration of the Ti elements decreased from the Ti side to the Ni side and the concentration distribution of the Ni elements showed the opposite trend, and the concentration changed in two steps within the narrow diffusion layers. There were two distinctive diffusion layers at the Ti/Ni interface distinguished by the color difference. The EDS point scanning analysis diagram (Fig. 2b) indicated two markedly different compounds. As the annealing time increased, the diffusion reaction occurred gradually and other new intermetallic phases formed along the original diffusion interface, creating a new diffusion layer. In addition, with the increase of annealing time, the intermetallic phases grew in the perpendicular direction along the diffusion interface and the thickness of the diffusion layers were gradually increased. The reaction diffusion of two elements can generate new solid solutions or new compounds. This was observed in the diffusion layer (Fig. 2a and 2c), as the spectra of Ti and Ni exhibit a wave rather than a line, which indicates that the diffusion region is not a single intermetallic compound layer [25]. The diffusion slope in Fig. 2a and 2c indicate that non-equilibrium solid solutions appeared in the interfaces and the reaction diffusion is uneven.

To identify the chemical composition of the new diffusion regions, EDS point scanning on SEM was performed in the vicinity of the Ti/Ni interfaces after annealed at 300°C for 1h and 60h as showed in Table 1 and 2. According to the Ti-Ni binary phase diagram and related report [19], we know that the interfaces between the Ti and Ni layers can produce intermetallic compounds including TiNi₃, TiNi, and Ti₂Ni phases. Typical points of 2 and 4 in Fig. 2b have a fixed ratio of Ti and Ni atoms, nearly similar to the chemical composition of intermetallic compounds TiNi and TiNi₃. According to the Ti-Ni binary phase diagram and the measured chemical composition, the average composition of 3 point in Fig. 2d is 49.26 at. % Ti and 50.74 at. % Ni, consistent with that of the TiNi phase. In the image shown in Fig. 2b, the point 2 adjacent side of Ni is TiNi phase similar the point 3 in Fig. 2d adjacent side of Ti and the thickness of TiNi phase increased as the holding time increased. With the extension of annealed time, the type of compound phases in the two sides of Ti/Ni interfaces change,

and the same phase will appear in different positions at different annealing times. The results also show that the thickness of different intermetallic compound layers exhibit different changes because the growth regularity of intermetallic compounds changed as the annealing time increased. As can be seen in Fig. 2b and 2d, the TiNi layer became thicker but the Ti₂Ni phase disappeared and was replaced by the TiNi₃ phase. This can be attributed to the formation and growth rule of intermetallic compounds, that is to say, it need to explain from two aspects of thermodynamics and kinetics. Youjing Zhang [20] found that the growth of intermetallics are divided into two stages. In the first stage, there is parabolic growth for all three phases, TiNi, Ti₂Ni, and TiNi₃. J.E. Garay [26] reached the same conclusion when they investigated Ti-Ni diffusion couples at temperatures ranging from 625 to 850°C. In the second stage, the growth of TiNi layers is still parabolic, but the growth rate is slower than that in the first stage. However, there is no detailed and accurate analysis of this process.

3.2 Mechanical properties

The tension curves of Ti/Ni laminated composites at room temperature are shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the laminated composites reveal different tensile properties at various annealing times. By increasing the annealing time, the tensile strength of the annealed samples decreased before 5h, slightly increased at 10h and 60h. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the composites annealed at 300 °C for 1h was 984.14MPa. After annealing at 300°C for 10h, the tensile strength reduced greatly with limited ductility. After annealing at 300°C for 1h, the elongation of the composites was 6.0%. Elongation of the sample annealing for 10h was the lowest. The tensile curves of annealed composites at 5h and 10h were very similar, consistent with the microstructure of the samples in Fig. 1.

3.3 Fractography

The fractographs of the Ti/Ni composites after tensile test are shown in Fig. 4. The fracture characteristics observed in the images in Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b are similar and it is obvious the mass of brittle fractures appeared in the Ti/Ni interface as the principal fracture accompanied by a small quantity of ductile fractures with some dimples and tear ridges around the dimples in the Ti layer. This indicates that brittle intermetallic compounds formed at the interface causing some brittle fractures. The ductility of Ti layer is better than that of the Ni layer. The fracture surface of the Ti layer exhibited microvoid coalescence leading to the formation of dimples [21]. The Ni layer also presented ductile fracture with traces of plastic deformation caused by the slip. On the microscale, the rock candy shape patterns indicated the local direction of crack propagation and implicated an intergranular brittle fracture (Fig. 4d).

To summarize, rock candy shape patterns, tearing ridges and many dimples were observed on the fracture surface of the annealed samples, indicating a mixed fracture mechanism of ductile mixed brittle fracture.

4 FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1: SEM images showing the interface microstructure of Ti/Ni multi-layered composites annealed at 300°C for different time (a) 1h, (b) 5h, (d) 10h, (e)60h

Figure 2: EDS line and point scan at the Ti/Ni composite: (a) and (b)annealed at 300°Cfor 1h, (c) and (d) annealed at 300°C for 60h

	1	2	3	4
Ti(at/%)	72.08	41.13	1.91	26.94
Ni(at/%)	27.92	58.87	98.09	73.06
Ti:Ni	Ti ₂ Ni	TiNi	Ni	TiNi ₃

Table 1: Chemical composition at different regions of Fig. 2b via EDS point analysis

	1	2	3	4	5
Ti(at/%)	99.97	58.54	49.26	26.09	2.22
Ni(at/%)	0.003	41.46	50.74	73.91	97.78

Ti:Ni	Ti	TiNi	TiNi	TiNi3	Ni
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Table 2: Chemical composition at different regions of Fig. 2d via EDS point analysis

Figure 3: Engineering stress–strain curves in tensile tests of laminated composites annealed at 300°C for different time

Figure 4: Tensile fractographs of the Ti/Ni rolled and annealed at 300°C for different time composite: (a) 1h, (b) 5h, (c) 10h, (d)60h

5 CONCLUSIONS

(1) For the annealed composite, some diffusion protuberances first appeared in the Ni layer. As the annealing time increased, the diffusion volume in the interfaces gradually increased. The EDS showed heterogeneous diffusion and intermetallic compounds of the two elements in the Ti/Ni interface.

(2) The tensile test showed the highest elongation of annealed composites at 300°C for 1h, 6.0%, and increase of 36% compared to the rolled samples. As annealing time increased, the tensile strength of the annealed samples decreased compared to the rolled sample and presented complicated changes, but the elongation value of the annealed composites increased dramatically.

(3) The fracture of the Ni layer showed the tip shape of a completely ductile fracture and many dimples in the Ti layer. There were fine transverse micro-cracks at the Ti/Ni interface, with intergranular brittle fracture. The fracture surface of the annealed samples revealed rock candy shape patterns, tearing ridges, and many dimples, indicating that the fracture mechanism is ductile mixed brittle fracture.

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